

EUPHRESOCO comprises 31 partners, 14 observers and 3 expert advisory bodies

PARTNERS

 The Food and Environment Research Agency, United Kingdom – **Coordinator**

Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Environment and Water Management, (BMEL/EUW)

 Austrian Agency for Health & Food Safety (AGES)

The Federal Public Service for Public Health, Food Chain Security & Environment (FPS)

 Walloon Agricultural Research Centre (GRA-W)

Ministry of the Flemish Community, Institute for Agricultural & Fisheries Research (ILVO)

Ministry of Agriculture & Forestry, National Service for Plant Protection (NSPP)

Ministry of Agriculture, National Agency for Agricultural Research (MZEL)

Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries, Danish Food Industry Agency (DFA)

Ministry of Agriculture, Research and Development Department (MAARD)

Ministry of Agriculture & Forestry (MKMF)

Ministry of Agriculture, Food, Fisheries & Rural Policy (MARP-DGAL)

National Institute of Agronomic Research (INRA)

The Federal Agency for Agriculture and Food (BLE)

Julius Kühn Institute (JKI)

Berndt Phytopathological Institute (BPI)

Department of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (DAFF)

Ministry of Agriculture & Forestry Policy (MIPAAF)

Agricultural Research Council (CRA)

Ministry of Agriculture (MA)

Ministry of Economic Affairs, Agriculture and Innovation (EL&I)

Ministry of Economic Affairs, Agriculture and Innovation, Plant Protection Service (NPPS)

Instituto Nacional de Recursos Biológicos (INRBI)

Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food (MAFF)

Ministry of Science and Innovation, National Institute for Agricultural and Food Research (INIA)

Federal Office of Agriculture, Division of Research & Extension (FOAG)

Ministry of Agriculture, Food & Rural Affairs, DG of Agriculture Research (MARA-GDAR)

Forestry Commission, Forest Research (FR)

Scottish Government, Science and Advice for Scottish Agriculture (SASA)

Institute of Plant Protection of National Academy of Agrarian Sciences of Ukraine (IPR NASU)

All-Russian Plant Quarantine Centre (FGU VNIKRI)

OBSERVERS

Ministry of Agriculture Natural Resources and Environment, Agricultural Research Institute

Central Agricultural Office, Directorate of Plant Protection and Soil Conservation

Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Latvia, State Plant Protection Service

Ministry of Agriculture Forestry and Water Economy, State Phytosanitary Laboratory (MAF-SPJ)

Ministry of resources and Rural Affairs, Plant Health Department

Bioteck, Plant Health and Plant Protection Division

Norwegian Forest and Landscape Institute

Institute of Plant Protection, National Research Institute

Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Rural Development, Central Laboratory for Phytosanitary Quarantine

The Swedish Research Council for Environment, Agricultural Science and Spatial Planning (FORMAS)

Department of Agriculture and Rural Development for Northern Ireland, Agrifood and Bioscience Institute, Applied Plant Science and Biometrics Division

USDA, Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service (APHIS), Plant Protection and Quarantine (PPQ)

CAB International (CABI)

EXPERT ADVISORY GROUP

Directorate General for Health and Consumer Protection (DG SANCO)

European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organisation (EPPO)

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

www.euphresco.org

Further Information

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European Phytosanitary
Research Coordination
**Coordinating Phytosanitary
Research to Help Protect
European Plant Health**
Integrating and Strengthening
the European Research Area (ERA)

EUPHRESOCO is funded by the
European Commission's
Seventh Framework
Programme (Coordination of
research activities),
Contract No. 265505 (ERAC) –
<http://cordis.europa.eu>

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Introduction

EUPHRESCO is an EU-funded ERA-NET under the 7th Framework Programme (FP7) and will run from 2011-2014. EUPHRESCO aims to continue as a self-sustainable, long-term network of European phytosanitary research funders after 2014. The project is a partnership of 31 leading organisations involved with funding phytosanitary (regulated plant health) research in 22 European countries.

Over the last century, the rate of introduction and establishment of new, economically or environmentally damaging plant pests and diseases has increased as a result of the expansion in global trade of plant material. Policy designed to protect Europe's agriculture and environment from these pest threats is determined at the EU level. However, the research that underpins policy is undertaken primarily at the national level with little coordination of programmes or activities.

EUPHRESCO will improve coordination and collaboration between national research programmes, thus ensuring effective support for EU policy and its implementation.

Strategic Objectives

EUPHRESCO aims to increase cooperation and coordination of national phytosanitary research programmes at EU level, to achieve three main strategic goals:

- Develop phytosanitary research policy at EU level.
- Optimise the research that underpins EU quarantine plant health policy development and implementation.
- Increase the capacity of European phytosanitary science and research.

These goals will be implemented through five workpackages:

- Workpackage 1** "Project coordination, management, communication and dissemination"
- Workpackage 2** "Implementing, testing and refining the proposed long-term, self-sustainable network structure"
- Workpackage 3** "Facilitating trans-national research projects"
- Workpackage 4** "Developing, refining and improving processes and tools for transnational cooperation"
- Workpackage 5** "Enlarging the network cooperation"

Benefits

EUPHRESCO provides a more cooperative and coordinated phytosanitary European Research Area (ERA) by involving key phytosanitary research funders and managers through:

- Sharing of information between national programmes.
- Coordination of existing national programmes at EU level.
- Developing common agendas based on identified, shared priorities.
- Developing proven instruments and mechanisms that will enable the implementation of joint trans-national activities.
- Creating a long-term, sustainable network of phytosanitary research programme funders.
- Improved interaction with stakeholders and industry bodies at national and EU levels.
- Establishing links between the Network and key research funding bodies around the world.
- Building European phytosanitary research capacity.

